

**Participatory Assessment of the Civic Engagement Capacity
of Local Organisations in Central Macedonia, Greece (WP2)**

Light Trees, Greece

March-April 2025

Funded by
the European Union

In Greece, the LISTEN project participatory needs assessment and community mapping took place across four key locations in Central Macedonia:

- Ano Poroia (Serres)
- Katerini (Pieria)
- Polykastro (Kilkis)
- Thessaloniki

Strengths of Community Organizations

Participatory Methodologies
Organizations involve residents in program design.

Effective Local Response
Small organizations quickly address local needs and crises.

Enhanced Communication
Small villages ensure residents are well-informed.

Economic Strengthening
Organizations boost the local economy and community bonds.

Community Organisations Face Deep-Rooted Challenges.

Funded by the European Union

Strengthening Organisational Capacity

Organisational Management

Core skills for effective operations

Volunteer Coordination

Skills to manage and engage volunteers

Strategic Planning

Skills for future-oriented decision-making

Community Development

Skills to foster community growth

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Strategy to Enhance Community Engagement

LISTEN

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**Participatory Assessment of the Civic Engagement
Capacity of Local Organisations in Topolovgrad,
Bulgaria (WP3)**

**Policy and Citizens' Observatory,
Bulgaria**

April 2025

Purpose, Scope, and Methodology

The **LISTEN** project participatory needs assessment and community mapping took place in Topolovgrad, in the south-eastern part of Bulgaria.

When: 28 – 30 April 2025

Participants: 40

How: Interviews and Focus groups

TOPOLOVGRAD COMMUNITY NEEDS

Topolovgrad Municipality

Access to Healthcare

- Only two doctors serve ~3,000 people each
- No fully functioning hospital in the town
- Mobile health services urgently needed

Volunteer & Emergency Support

- Lack of formal civil protection structure
- No state-level disaster prevention planning

Educational Support

- School-aged children left behind due to family migration
- High-school quality insufficient; families send to Plovdiv
- Need for youth skills training and digital literacy

- 1 town and 20 villages—with a total **population** of around **8,941**.
- ethnically **diverse**, with approximately 8% Roma.
- **negative population growth** and **aging demographics**.
 - with **39%** of Haskovo Province's population **at risk of poverty or social exclusion**.

Infrastructure & Transport

- Poor transport links to regional centers
- Isolated villages lack bus service
- Difficult access to school, services, jobs

Employment and Economic Stability

- Decline of key sectors: mining, tailoring, medical supply
- Few job opportunities, especially for women and youth
- Temporary work programs too limited

Inclusion and Participation

- Barriers to inclusion
- Gaps in NGO/municipality collaboration
- Need for formal/social recognition of grassroots efforts

KEY ORGANISATIONAL NEEDS

Sustainable Funding

- Reliance on ad-hoc support and donations.
- Lack of core funding for cultural, volunteer, and youth groups.
- Emergency responders receive minimal and delayed state support.

Technical Resources & Equipment

- Volunteer teams lack basic equipment (protective gear, transport, tools).
- Cultural institutions operate with outdated infrastructure and limited digital tools

Monitoring & Visibility

- No systems for tracking impact or scaling successful initiatives.
- Need for communication strategies to highlight local efforts nationally and internationally.

Training & Capacity Building

- Need for skills in community mobilisation, NGO management, and accessing EU/national funding.
- Some require guidance on forming formal entities to participate in projects.

Institutional/Social Support & Recognition

- Grassroots efforts sometimes lack social acknowledgement and integration into state strategies.
- Volunteers are often overburdened without structural backing or legal protection.

Communication & Networking

- Need for improved collaboration between civic actors, schools, NGOs, and the municipality.
- Better networking with regional/national/international peers to exchange practices and access joint funding.

KEY STRENGTHS OF COMMUNITY ORGANISATIONS

Strong Volunteer Culture

- Deep-rooted traditions of mutual aid and solidarity.
- Volunteers are highly active in emergency response, despite limited resources.

Cultural Institutions as Civic Hubs

- The community cultural centre engages over 250 residents—spanning dance, theatre, music, and literary groups.
- Acts as a unifying space, inclusive of ethnic groups and all age groups.

Active School Involvement

- Schools participate in regular solidarity actions such as bazaars and charity events.
- Educational mediators play a key role in linking families, teachers, and vulnerable students.

High Public Trust in Local Leaders

- The mayor and key civic figures model active participation and care.
- Their involvement encourages broad community engagement and legitimizes grassroots initiatives.

Inclusivity & Low Polarisation

- Organisations maintain a strong anti-discrimination ethic.
- Activities are open to all ethnicities and ages, with special outreach to Roma communities.

Creativity & Innovation in Engagement

- Use of cultural production (concerts, bazaars, dance shows, theatre festivals) to mobilise support and tell local stories.

STRENGTHENING ORGANISATIONAL CAPACITY

01

Expand Youth Skill Development

- Projects that build public speaking, teamwork, and digital/media skills.
- Address current gaps in soft skills and confidence for regional competitions or employment.

02

Foster Intergenerational and Intersectional Participation

- Use creative projects (films, interviews, photos) to connect youth with older residents and restore appreciation for lost professions and local history.

03

Strengthen Community Visibility

- Use local media and international exhibitions (e.g., the LISTEN project platform) to showcase civic efforts.
- Promote a positive narrative of Topolovgrad as “the town of good deeds.”

04

Scalability

Develop replicable models for community capacity building

05

Valuing Informal Participation

In Topolovgrad, much civic life happens informally. These actions often go unrecorded but are key to social cohesion. Recognising and supporting this invisible work is essential for strengthening long-term civic engagement.

REPLICABLE PRACTICES IDENTIFIED IN TOPOLOVGRAD

Operational efficiency

Themed Charity Bazaars

- Regular, well-attended events (Fridays, holidays) that raise funds for specific causes (e.g., medical treatments, house fires).
- Organised by schools, community centres, and informal youth groups with high participation and transparency.

Community Centre Programming

- Cultural groups (dance, theatre, vocal, poetry) engage over 250 residents.
- Strong ethos of inclusion: no political divisions, multiethnic participation, and intergenerational involvement.

Volunteer Educational Mediators

- Bridge between school, home, and marginalised communities (esp. Roma).
- Provide emotional and logistical support for students at risk of dropping out.

Environmental Campaigns

- Tree planting, bird counts, and participation in “Let’s Clean Bulgaria Together.”
- Mobilises citizens of all ages and fosters civic responsibility.

Youth Documentary Projects (Planned)

- Intergenerational initiative involving schoolchildren creating video portraits of retired workers from vanished industries (e.g., sewing, mining).
- Builds media literacy, teamwork, and civic empathy.

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Participatory Assessment of the Civic Engagement Capacity of Local Organisations in Verona, Italy (WP4)

Oriel APS, Italy
March-May 2025

VERONA, ITALY

A major city in
Northern Italy
with
255,000
residents

Economy

Tourism

High
quality
of life

Infrastructure

Industry

Logistics

Dynamic yet
complex landscape
for inclusive
civic action

KEY CAPACITIES ANALYSED

KEY STRENGTHS

- **WIDESPREAD CIVIC SPACES**

Local centres and neighbourhood hubs for dialogue and community action

- **RESILIENT INFORMAL NETWORKS**

Trust-based alliances and shared ethical orientations

- **STRATEGIC IMPACT FACTORS**

Long-term presence and integrated methods

- **EFFECTIVE SOLIDARITY ACTIONS**

Support for vulnerable groups through tailored initiatives

- **STRATEGIC IMPACT FACTORS**

Long-term presence and integrated methods

KEY WEAKNESSES

The assessment identified critical weaknesses that hinder inclusive and sustainable impact.

A. LIMITED RESOURCES

- Short-term funding
- Volunteer burnout
- Lack of core funding
- Scarce infrastructure

B. METHODOLOGICAL GAPS

- Few training options
- Intuition over tools
- Limited peer learning
- Inadequate skills

C. BARRIERS TO INCLUSION

- Hard-to-reach groups
- Participation gap
- Disconnect from realities

Key Organisational Needs

A Need for Stable and Flexible Funding

Organisations lack core and multi-year funding

Project-based financing leads to instability, fragmented work, and inability to plan long-term

B Need for Sustainable Human Resource Structures

Heavy reliance on volunteers creates burnout and turnover

Demand for paid, stable roles to ensure continuity and inclusiveness in operations

C Need for Continuous Capacity Building

Desire for training in inclusive facilitation, digital tools, and co-design methods

Lack of structured mentoring or peer-learning systems

D Need for Adequate Infrastructure and Digital Access

Gaps in physical and digital infrastructure limit reach and efficiency

Outdated tools and insufficient training hinder digital transition

E Need for Ecosystem-Level Coordination and Visibility

Absence of coordinated networks and shared platforms

Weak links with institutions reduce visibility and policy influence

Key recommendations to strengthen organisational capacity

- Develop continuous and contextualised training programmes
- Facilitate access to sustainable and flexible funding
- Promote cross-sector partnerships and strategic alliances
- Create local platforms for civic coordination and knowledge sharing
- Invest in organizational wellbeing and staff sustainability
- Provide micro-grants and seed funding for local initiatives
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- Establish a municipal liaison for civic organisations
- Foster participatory evaluation and community feedback mechanisms
- Support inclusive digital transformation for civic actors
- Encourage youth leadership and intergenerational collaboration
- Foster participatory evaluation for civic actors

Enhancing community engagement key recommendations

Develop culturally sensitive and inclusive outreach strategies

Build long-term relationships through presence and trust

Meet people where they are

Document and value informal participation

Create safe and welcoming spaces for expression

Document and value informal participation

Foster intergenerational and intersectional participation

Activate peer-led engagement models

Reframe engagement as mutual learning and transformation

Addressing identified needs and gaps – key recommendations

**Conduct continuous
and participatory
needs assessments**

**Design tailored
and modular
interventions**

**Prioritise support
services that enable
participation**

**Leverage existing
micro-networks and
trust structures**

**Address internal gaps
in strategic planning
and evaluation**

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WE LISTEN WE BUILD

Diving into civic engagement and
community-building across Europe

Identified Good Practices

The experience of RedeMOVE shows how local collaboration can evolve into sustainable and impactful community solutions.

- RedeMOVE started as informal collaboration between local NGOs and developed into a well-structured and effective network.

- Community-centred practices, participatory methodologies, psychological support, informal education, cultural and sports activities.

- Tangible impact through co-created projects: community radio, inclusive skateboarding, festivals, and EU literacy.

- Built on shared values, trust, and strong ties with the communities.

- Active youth involvement through volunteering, urban art, and participatory media.

Identified Needs

The assessment process revealed structural challenges that affect both communities and the organisations that work with them.

Needs of the communities:

- Accessible and inclusive digital communication: lack of a centralised, clear channel limits participation, especially among those with low digital literacy.
- Discrimination and exclusion: xenophobia, racism, sexism, homophobia and transphobia remain major barriers to participation. Major barriers to participatio. The rise of hate crimes and hate speech, demand new protective measures for NGO workers and community members
- Transport in the Algarve: limited public transport and isolated rural areas make access to opportunities more difficult — particularly relevant given our regional base.

Needs of the organisations:

- Structural and continuous funding.
- Digital and logistical staff support (e.g. communication, websites, evaluation, project management), including lack of funds and time to build digital skills due to staff overload.
- Dedicated spaces and shared infrastructure. Use of public spaces for communities to engage and participate.
- Institutional recognition of non-formal education and informal cultural practices (e.g. hip hop, graffiti).

POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

From concrete tools to creative ideas, several proposals emerged to address the identified needs.

- POP-UP Solidarity Van: a mobile unit that brings therapies, creative workshops and inclusive activities to remote or underserved areas.

- Wellbeing programme for NGO staff: retreats, mental health support and collective activities to prevent burnout.

- Youth digital portal: a user-friendly app with events, micro-funding calls and chatbot access.

- Micro-funding for youth-led initiatives: accessible, low-barrier funding with participatory selection.

- Short-term training (“bootcamps”) in inclusive communication, AI, and participatory evaluation.

- Shared resource agreements: logistics, vehicles, equipment and materials pooled among local organisations.

Key Recommendations

Strategic steps to strengthen organisations and boost inclusive community participation.

1. Strengthen organisational capacity

- Establish a solidarity fund (supported by municipalities, private donors and philanthropy).
- Offer mentorship programmes and peer learning in collaboration with universities.
- Set up shared services for digital tools, logistics, legal support, and communication.
- Promote long-term funding models and formal partnerships with local authorities.

2. Increase community engagement

- Create inclusive communication strategies with the help of youth ambassadors.
- Launch a structured RedeMOVE volunteering
- Ensure hybrid participation formats (live events + livestreams + digital surveys).
- Develop a shared services catalogue with QR codes for quick access.
- Provide community co-designed spaces, including public areas and NGO facilities, as well as solidarity transport passes.

Thank you for your listening!

We are very interested in your reflections and welcome all questions.

<https://thelistenproject.eu/>

<https://contextos.org.pt/>